
Synthesis of silica nanoparticles coating with gold nanoparticles and its application

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Abstract SiO₂ nanoparticles have been successfully synthesized by modification of the preparation method of SiO₂ nanoparticles, which prepared by seed growth process using Ethanol, Tetra Ortho Silicate (TEOS) and Ammonia Solution (NH₄OH). Then, the SiO₂ nanoparticles were coated with gold nanoparticles. In this study, a new preparation of SiO₂ nanoparticles is reported. The characterization of SiO₂ nanoparticles are done by TEM, XRD and UV.

Keywords SiO₂ nanoparticles, Gold Nanoparticle and characterization of SiO₂ nanoparticles.

Introduction

The Stober process is used for the preparation of monodispersed silica colloids "white carbon black" by means of hydrolysis of alkyl silicates and subsequent condensation of silicic acid in alcoholic solutions using ammonia as catalyst [1-6]. There are many research groups who applied those monodispersed silica colloids as model material in various applications. The preparation of silica particles of irregular shape have been investigated extensively, but synthesis of silica particles of uniform size and shape is not common [2-6]. Silica particles have been extensively used as templates in the fabrication of polymeric capsules due to its mono disperse nature and highly porous surface structure. It is very important to control the size, shape and surface morphology of the particles. Silica particles size ranges from nanometre to micron were synthesized by different routes [7]. The structure of colloidal particles may vary from isolated spherical particles to agglomerates of complex structure [8]. Common issues associated with silica particle synthesis are poly dispersity and meso porous orientation [9-12]. Colloidal particles with uniform size, shape and composition finds wider applications in industry [13-17]. Mono dispersity is one of the major requirements of template synthesis for the capsule preparation. This study deals with the development of mono disperse silica particles of uniform size by seeded growth method by the continuous addition of TEOS to improve mono dispersity, size and shape of the particles in sustained drug delivery applications.

Experimental Work

Materials: TEOS (Tetra Ethylene Ortho Silicate), NH₄OH and C₂H₅OH were obtained from China and deionized water from lab.

Table 1: General Characteristics of Ethyl Silicate

Molecular formula	Ethyl Silicate (C ₈ H ₂₀ O ₄ Si)
Appearance	Liquid
Density 20 °C (g/ml)	0.932–0.936
Molecular weight	208.33
SiO₂	≥ 28.4 %
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Table 2: General Characteristics of Ethanol

Molecular formula	Ethanol (C ₂ H ₆ O)≥99.7%
Appearance	Liquid
Density 20 °C (g/ml)	0.789–0.791
Molecular weight	46.07
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Table 3: General Characteristics of Ammonia Solution

Molecular formula	Ammonia Solution (NH ₄ OH)
Appearance	liquid
Molecular weight	17.03
Content	25 - 28 %
Company	Sinopharm chemical reagent Co ,Ltd ,China

Figure 2: SEM of AuNPs Ethanol

Figure 3: SEM of AuNPs+SiO₂+PVP+Ethanol

Figure 4: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Figure 5: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Figure 6: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Figure 7: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Figure 8: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Figure 9: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

Figure 10: TEM of Silica Nanoparticles at 30 °C

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Figure 11: XRD for Silica Nanoparticles

Figure 12: UV SiO₂ Nanoparticles

Figure 13: UV GNPs Coating SiO₂ Nanoparticles

Synthesis of Silica nanoparticles

Silica nanoparticles were prepared by mixing 0.5 mL of tetra Ethylene Ortho Silicate (TEOS), 50 mL ethanol and 10 mL aqueous ammonia (NH₄OH) under repaid stirring condition for 24 hours and temperature 30 °C. After stirring the mixture, 7 mL TEOS was added drop wise and SiO₂ particles were separated from solution by centrifugation at 10000 rpm and washed three times with deionized water and pure ethanol.

The synthesized silica nanoparticles suspension was dried in oven at 65 °C for 24 hours.

Synthesis Au@SiO₂ Core/shell Solid spheres

Monodisperse gold nanoparticles were prepared according to Frens' method [19] in briefly we took 400 mL deionized water boiling at 150 °C, 20 mg (HAuCl₄.3H₂O) we taken 3.0 ml in to the solution in flask with vigorous stirring. Then when temperature reached 150 °C after 10 min. Sodium citrate containing (0.14g dissolved 2 ml deionized water we took 1 ml of Solution and injected quickly to the solution. The mixture was refluxed for 30 min. Then cooled to room temperature. An aqueous solution PVP (12.8 g/L, 0.235 mL) was added to the colloidal gold solution to modify the gold nanoparticle surface to facilitate silica coating .The solution was stirred for 24 hours at room temperature to guarantee complete absorption of PVP. The PVP Functionalized gold nanoparticles were collected by centrifugation and redispersed in 4 mL Water. In typical silica coating process, (10 mL) gold nanoparticles covered by PVP (1 mL) was in to solution containing mixing 0.4 ml of tetra Ethylene Ortho Silicate (TEOS), 50 ml ethanol

and 10 ml aqueous ammonia (NH₄OH) under repaid stirring condition for 24 hours at temperature 30 °C . After stirring the mixture, 7 ml TEOS was added drop wise under vigorous stirring.

Silica nanoparticles coating gold nanoparticles were separated from solution by centrifugation at 10000 rpm and washed three times with deionized water and pure ethanol. The Synthesized silica particle suspension was dried in oven at 65 °C for 24 hours.

Results and Discussion

Silica nanoparticle gets in 30 °C. Figure 1(SEM), figure 2 (SEM) AuNPs and figure 3 (SEM) Silica coating AuNPs and (SEM) shows the top-view SEM images of the Coating Silica nanoparticle figure 3 (SEM). TEM images of the Silica nanoparticle figure 4-10(TEM). A silica particle is seen and the size of the Silica nanoparticle is about 0.42 μm from SEM photo. The size SiO₂ nanoparticle can be seen from TEM image and is about 0.47 μm.

SEM Results

Silicon wafer were cut into (3mm x 3mm) pieces and used Piranha solution [18] for cleaning of Silicon wafer. Then followed by triple rinsing in ethanol with ultrasonic cleaning for 30 min then used nitrogen (N₂) for drying. Then small amount of sample was placed on Si wafer for SEM test.

TEM Tests

For TEM Test, a small amount of sample was dissolved in test tube and 3mL of deionized water was added to it and the solution was stirred by ultra-sonication. Then 10 μ L solutions was transferred to clean Copper Grid And kept for drying for TEM test.

UV Results

For UV results, a small amount of sample in test tube and then was dissolved in 3mL deionized water into the sample and the mix solution was stirred by ultra-sonication to make sure the sample was uniform. Then transferred solution was to cavity of spectrophotometer machine to get the test. Spectra were recorded at 300 to 750 nm shown in the figure 12 and 13.

XRD Result

For XRD results, a small amount of powder sample in to XRD machine is record between intensity and degree (2θ) shown in the figure11.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the synthesis method for SiO₂ was modified. The Main applications of Silica Nanoparticles are in sustained drug delivery applications. The surface and size can be seen from the TEM image.

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